

D4.2

OJS core feature enhancements

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Abstract	<p>This deliverable (D4.2) presents the completed core enhancements to Open Journal Systems (OJS) developed within the CRAFT-OA project's Work Package 4. The work improves OJS in three areas: data privacy, multilingual publishing, and metadata quality. These developments were carried out collaboratively by TSV, TIB, and PKP, and all results have been submitted to PKP's public repositories.</p> <p>A significant share of the work is included in the OJS 3.5 release, including GDPR-compliant user and role management and major multilingualism improvements. The remaining completed developments, primarily related to metadata quality and extensibility, are scheduled for release in OJS 3.6. Together, these contributions reinforce the technical foundation, interoperability, and long-term sustainability of PKP's publishing ecosystem and support the growth of Diamond Open Access</p>

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Disclaimer

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List of Acronyms

API	Application Programming Interface
BCP 47	Internet Best Current Practices 47 Language Tags
CRedit	Contributor Role Taxonomy
DOAJ	Directory of Open Access Journals
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
ID	Identifier
ISSN	International Standard Serial Number
OJS	Open Journal Systems
OMP	Open Monograph Press
OPS	Open Preprint Systems
ORCID	Open Researcher and Contributor ID
PKP	Public Knowledge Project
ROR	Research Organization Registry
SEO	Search Engine Optimization
UI	User Interface

URI	Uniform Resource Identifier
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
XML	Extensible Markup Language

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1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable, D4.2 – OJS core feature enhancements, published on GitHub, documented in a public issue tracker, submitted for inclusion by PKP, is part of Work Package 4 (WP4): Journal Software and Platform Improvement within the CRAFT-OA project. It focuses on enhancing Open Journal Systems (OJS) core functionalities in three key areas: Data Privacy and General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) compliance (Task 4.1), Multilingualism (Task 4.1), and Metadata Quality and Extensibility (Task 4.3).

The development work has been carried out by [the Federation of Finnish Learned Societies \(TSV\)](#) and the [TIB – Leibniz Information Centre for Science and Technology and University Library](#), in collaboration with the [Public Knowledge Project \(PKP\)](#), the main developer of OJS. All new features have been published in public PKP repositories, documented in the open issue tracker, and submitted for inclusion in official OJS releases.

The GDPR and data privacy developments strengthen compliance with the GDPR through a new invitation-based process for users and roles management. Editors can invite users to join the platform or assume roles, ensuring all actions require explicit consent. This mechanism lays the foundation for future privacy and user management improvements across PKP applications.

The multilingualism improvements introduce a more flexible and sustainable language management system. Journals can now configure interface, submission, and metadata languages independently, enabling multilingual metadata even without corresponding UI translations. Editors can modify the submission language at any stage, and all language versions are now discoverable through crawler indexing. Adoption of Internet Best Current Practices 47 Language Tags (BCP 47) language tags¹ extends support to regional and minority languages, improving inclusivity and discoverability.

The metadata quality and extensibility updates establish a stronger foundation for structured, machine-readable metadata. OJS now supports controlled vocabularies, allowing metadata terms such as keywords and disciplines to be linked to authoritative sources. The work also includes structured contributor metadata for persons, organizations, and anonymous contributors, and implements Contributor Role Taxonomy (CRediT) roles for standardized attribution of contributions. In addition, support for data citations enables journals to record and export links between publications and related datasets using persistent identifiers. Together, these features improve metadata interoperability and alignment with international standards and services such as Crossref, DataCite, and OpenAIRE.

These developments benefit all users of PKP software – including OJS, Open Monograph Press (OMP), and Open Preprint Systems (OPS) – reinforcing the

¹ Phillips, A., & Davis, M. (2009). Tags for Identifying Languages (RFC 5646: Best Current Practice 47). Internet Engineering Task Force. Retrieved from <https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/html/rfc5646>.

technical foundation and sustainability of Diamond Open Access publishing in Europe and beyond.

2 OPEN JOURNAL SYSTEMS RELEASES AND INCLUSION OF CRAFT-OA DEVELOPMENTS

Open Journal Systems (OJS) 3.5 was officially released by the Public Knowledge Project (PKP) in June 2025 and is the first version of OJS to include core feature contributions developed within the CRAFT-OA project. The release integrates major results from Tasks 4.1 and 4.3, including improvements in data privacy and General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) compliance, multilingualism, and metadata quality. These developments strengthen OJS's technical foundation, improve compliance and interoperability, and enhance its suitability for multilingual Diamond Open Access publishing.

The forthcoming OJS 3.6 release, planned for 2026, will continue this work by incorporating the remaining developments from Task 4.3 related to metadata extensibility. These will expand contributor and metadata handling and further improve alignment with international standards. Detailed descriptions of the implemented features are provided in the following sections.

CRAFT-OA Task	Feature Area	Description	OJS Release	Lead Developer
T4.1	Data Privacy and GDPR	Invitation-based users and roles management	3.5	TIB
T4.1	Multilingualism	All planned multilingualism features	3.5	TSV
T4.3	Metadata Quality and Extensibility	Controlled vocabularies	3.5	TSV
T4.3	Metadata Quality and Extensibility	Contributors' metadata, data citations, metadata checks	3.6	TIB & TSV

Table 1: Inclusion of CRAFT-OA developments in OJS releases

3 DATA PRIVACY AND GDPR

The GDPR work described in this section is part of CRAFT-OA Work Package 4: Journal Software and Platform Improvement, under Task 4.1. The development work has been done by the TIB – Leibniz Information Centre for Science and Technology and University Library. The work addresses GDPR compliance requirements for OJS/ Open Monograph Press (OMP)/ Open Preprint Systems (OPS) and improves invitation based role creation for users and reviewers. It also includes User Interface (UI) improvements, bug fixes and enhanced extensibility across both backend and frontend components.

3.1 Technical & Implementation Considerations

Earlier OJS 3.3 releases lacked sufficient mechanisms for managing consent, data retention, and user information in accordance with European data protection standards. These gaps complicated lawful data handling, especially in reviewer invitations and user profile management. Highlighting these deficiencies clarifies the need for the GDPR-compliant improvements introduced in OJS 3.5.

Correct creation of users and reviewers within the journal-wide invitation process had to be ensured through a refactoring of the shared database structures. This refactoring has now been completed, and full compatibility is ensured. During invitation acceptance, weaknesses in handling authentication states were identified, indicating that parts of the existing design were not sufficiently robust. To address these issues, the relevant design components were enhanced. As a result, authentication handling within the invitation process is now more consistent and reliable across all journals. Updates to the user Application Programming Interface (API) required close coordination to maintain integration stability. Differences between implemented features and [Figma](#) designs highlighted opportunities for improving specification clarity and review processes.

3.2 Project Management & Quality Considerations

Edge-case testing across distributed teams, onboarding inexperienced developers and the additional micro-management required from TIB's technical management revealed areas for improvement in future applications. OJS Release milestone deadlines encouraged balancing GDPR compliance with release stability, leading to multiple refinement cycles. Strengthening upfront specification review and mockup approvals could further improve development efficiency and reduce the need for iterative enhancements.

3.3 Regulatory & Requirements Considerations

Differences in interpreting GDPR requirements, matching global privacy perspective of OJS with GDPR requirements sometimes led to differing viewpoints between product owner (PKP) and the community. Ambiguities in defining “consent” resulted in multiple interpretation cycles, and coordinating multilingual requirements and GDPR-specific legal terminology introduced additional discussion points.

3.4 Github issues and pull requests for GDPR and Data Privacy features

The following list documents the core GitHub issues and pull requests related to the GDPR compliance work carried out in CRAFT-OA Task 4.1. Each entry links to the technical implementation of new privacy and data protection features developed for OJS and related PKP applications (OMP, OPS, and shared libraries).

The screenshot shows the 'Journal of Public Knowledge' interface. On the left is a navigation menu with categories like Submissions, Settings, Statistics, and Tools. The main content area is titled 'Invite user to take a role' and includes a breadcrumb 'USERS & ROLES > USERS > Invite user to take a role'. Below the title is a progress indicator with three steps: '1 Search user', '2 Enter details', and '3 Review email & invite for roles'. The current step is 'STEP 1 - SEARCH USER', which contains instructions: 'Search for the user using their email address, username or ORCID ID. Enter at least one detail to get started. If the user does not exist, you can invite them to take up roles and be a part of your journal. If the user already exists in the journal, you can view user entered information and invite them to take additional roles.' There are three input fields: 'Email address' (with example 'e.g. aeinstein@example.com'), 'Username' (with example 'e.g. mickeymouse'), and 'ORCID ID' (with example 'e.g. 0000-0000-0000-0000'). A '1234-5678-9101-1121' is entered in the ORCID ID field. At the bottom right are 'Cancel' and 'Search user' buttons.

Figure 1: Newly added Invitation-based workflow in OJS replacing the previous user-creation process.

Both implemented features (user and reviewer invitation) are specified and documented as a visual story in open tickets:

- <https://github.com/pkp/pkp-lib/issues/9658>
- <https://github.com/pkp/pkp-lib/issues/9659>

Additionally, the design document is available for the public.

Task	T4.1 Data Privacy (User and Reviewer invitation)
Subtask	User invitation and Reviewer invitation
Github specification issues	https://github.com/pkp/pkp-lib/issues/9658 (user invitation) https://github.com/pkp/pkp-lib/issues/9659 (reviewer invitation)
Pull request and comments for backend support	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. https://github.com/pkp/pkp-lib/pull/9796 2. https://github.com/pkp/pkp-lib/pull/10516 3. https://github.com/pkp/pkp-lib/pull/10558 4. https://github.com/pkp/pkp-lib/pull/10576 5. https://github.com/pkp/pkp-lib/pull/10588 6. https://github.com/pkp/pkp-lib/pull/10644 7. https://github.com/pkp/pkp-lib/pull/10888 8. https://github.com/pkp/pkp-lib/pull/10895 9. https://github.com/pkp/pkp-lib/pull/10990 10. https://github.com/pkp/pkp-lib/pull/11009 11. https://github.com/pkp/pkp-lib/pull/11010 12. https://github.com/pkp/pkp-lib/pull/11216 13. https://github.com/pkp/pkp-lib/pull/10557 14. https://github.com/pkp/pkp-lib/pull/10536 15. https://github.com/pkp/pkp-lib/pull/11266 16. https://github.com/pkp/pkp-lib/pull/11271 17. https://github.com/pkp/pkp-lib/pull/11272 18. https://github.com/pkp/pkp-lib/pull/11274 19. https://github.com/pkp/pkp-lib/pull/11293 20. https://github.com/pkp/pkp-lib/pull/11324
Pull request and comments for UI support pkp/ui-lib	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. https://github.com/pkp/ui-library/pull/358 2. https://github.com/pkp/ui-library/pull/362 3. https://github.com/pkp/ui-library/pull/374 4. https://github.com/pkp/ui-library/pull/382 5. https://github.com/pkp/ui-library/pull/437 6. https://github.com/pkp/ui-library/pull/439 7. https://github.com/pkp/ui-library/pull/441 8. https://github.com/pkp/ui-library/pull/450 9. https://github.com/pkp/ui-library/pull/465 10. https://github.com/pkp/ui-library/pull/496 11. https://github.com/pkp/ui-library/pull/511 12. https://github.com/pkp/ui-library/pull/513 13. https://github.com/pkp/ui-library/pull/515 14. https://github.com/pkp/ui-library/pull/516 15. https://github.com/pkp/ui-library/pull/533 16. https://github.com/pkp/ui-library/pull/537 17. https://github.com/pkp/ui-library/pull/578 18. https://github.com/pkp/ui-library/pull/587 19. https://github.com/pkp/ui-library/pull/588 20. https://github.com/pkp/ui-library/pull/589 21. https://github.com/pkp/ui-library/pull/590 22. https://github.com/pkp/ui-library/pull/598 23. https://github.com/pkp/ui-library/pull/599 24. https://github.com/pkp/ui-library/pull/624

	25. https://github.com/pkp/ui-library/pull/625
OJS Application	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. https://github.com/pkp/ojs/pull/48922. https://github.com/pkp/ojs/pull/4893
OPS Application	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. https://github.com/pkp/ops/pull/978
OMP Application	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. https://github.com/pkp/omp/pull/1989

Table 2: T4.1 Data Privacy work in Github.

4 MULTILINGUALISM

The multilingualism work described in this section is part of CRAFT-OA Work Package 4: Journal Software and Platform Improvement, under Task 4.1. The development work has been done by the Federation of Finnish Learned Societies (TSV) and focuses on enhancing multilingual functionality in OJS. It includes identifying structural issues in earlier versions and developing improvements that strengthen multilingual publishing capabilities in OJS 3.5.

4.1 Challenges in multilingualism support

OJS has long provided comprehensive support for multilingual publishing. The platform allows journals to offer their UI, submission workflow, and publication metadata in several languages, making it possible to publish multilingual content and to reach diverse readerships around the world.

However, the CRAFT-OA project identified a number of structural limitations in how multilingual functionality was implemented in OJS 3.4 and earlier versions. Many of these issues had already been recognized and discussed within the PKP community.²

4.1.1 Single language setting controlling both interface and content

OJS uses one shared language system for all multilingual functionality. The same locale setting defines the available languages for the UI, forms, and submissions. Because of this, only languages that have a full application locale (i.e., UI translation) can be used for content or metadata.

This model excludes smaller, regional, or historical languages that do not have official OJS locales. Journals are therefore forced to create unofficial locales that do not contain any actual localisation data or to store data under incorrect language codes, which leads to poor metadata quality and long-term maintenance issues.

² Examples of existing discussion in the PKP Forum: <https://forum.pkp.sfu.ca/t/adding-a-new-locale-language-on-ojs-for-a-language-without-an-iso-639-1-code/78990>
<https://forum.pkp.sfu.ca/t/adding-support-for-new-language-specifying-language-of-the-article-submission-latvian/10035>
<https://forum.pkp.sfu.ca/t/article-language-change/11269>
<https://forum.pkp.sfu.ca/t/ojs-2-4-8-3-how-can-i-change-the-language-of-submission/53906>
<https://forum.pkp.sfu.ca/t/ojs3-google-is-indexing-only-1-language-per-url/27443>
<https://forum.pkp.sfu.ca/t/isnt-there-a-different-url-to-different-languages/57712>

4.1.2 No separation between website and metadata language settings

The same configuration applies to both the site interface and submission metadata. Journals that want to publish in one language but provide metadata—such as titles and abstracts—in several languages are not fully supported. The Forms setting applies only to the context (site) level, not to submissions. Consequently, multilingual metadata fields cannot be enabled without also allowing submissions in those same languages.

4.1.3 Metadata tied to submission language availability

Metadata forms depend on the Submissions language setting, even for previously published content. If a journal has older articles in a language that is later disabled for submissions, the metadata for those articles can no longer be edited. Journals often keep obsolete locales active solely to preserve the ability to maintain older content, which leads to unnecessary clutter and administrative overhead.

4.1.4 Multiple overlapping language fields

OJS stores language information in several locations. In addition to the submission-level language chosen at the start of the process, editors can enable a separate metadata field for language. The relationship between these fields is unclear, and editors often do not know which one affects which part of the workflow or export. This results in confusion and inconsistent metadata management.

4.1.5 Publication language locked after submission

Once the submission language is selected, it cannot be changed later in the editorial workflow. If the wrong language is selected, editors have no safe way to correct it. Many journals try to fix the problem by editing the database directly or by entering metadata under the wrong language, which can lead to corrupted data.

4.1.6 No language-specific URL structure

OJS does not include the selected language in the Uniform Resource Locator (URL) structure. The current language selection is stored in a browser cookie instead of being represented in the page URL. As a result, each page or article has only one URL, regardless of the language in which it is viewed.

For crawlers, alternative language versions are completely inaccessible because they have no unique URLs to follow. This prevents search engines and other automated services from indexing or harvesting multilingual metadata correctly.

4.2 New multilingualism features in OJS 3.5

With the release of OJS 3.5, several long-standing limitations in multilingual functionality have been addressed. The improvements introduce a more flexible and sustainable multilingual architecture. The new features enhance how OJS manages languages across the interface, submissions, metadata, and URLs, allowing journals to better support complex multilingual publishing workflows.³

4.2.1 Decoupling UI, submission, and metadata language settings

OJS 3.5 introduces a restructured language management system that separates UI, submission, and metadata languages. Previously, all three were tightly coupled to the installed application locales. Now, journals can independently define which languages are available for UI display, submissions, and metadata. This allows multilingual metadata entry in languages that do not have corresponding UI translations and eliminates the dependency on application locales for metadata availability.

4.2.2 Flexible support for additional languages using BCP 47

Metadata and submission languages are now defined according to the BCP 47 language standard, providing access to more than 700 codes, including script and regional variants (e.g. *fr_CA*, *cnr_Cyrl*). This ensures interoperability with other metadata systems and supports regional, minority, and historical languages that were previously excluded. Editors can add metadata in any valid BCP 47 language tag regardless of interface language.

³ Nygård, A.-J. (2024, September 26). CRAFT-OA brings multilingual improvements to Open Journal Systems 3.5. CRAFT-OA. <https://www.craft-oa.eu/craft-oa-brings-multilingual-improvements-to-open-journal-systems-3-5/>

Website Languages				
Locale	Code	Primary locale	UI	Forms
▶ English/English	en	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
▶ French/français	fr_CA	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
▶ Finnish/suomi	fi	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

Submission Languages				Add/Remove Languages
Locale	Code	Default	Submissions	Metadata
English/English	en	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Finnish/suomi	fi	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
French (Canada)/français (Canada)	fr_CA	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Southern Sami/eteläsaame	sma	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

Figure 2: OJS 3.5 separates the UI language and Submission metadata language and adds support for hundreds of new metadata languages.

4.2.3 Independent metadata editing for legacy content

Metadata fields are no longer dependent on the Submissions language setting. Journals can edit multilingual metadata for previously published articles even when submissions in those languages are disabled. This change removes the prior requirement to keep obsolete locales active solely to maintain older content.

4.2.4 Editable and visible submission language in the workflow

The submission's primary language is now clearly displayed in the editorial interface and can be modified at any stage of the workflow. When the language is changed, required metadata fields are demanded for the new language. This prevents mismatches between the stored language and the actual content, improving metadata accuracy and editorial control.

Figure 3: Submission language can be changed during the editorial workflow.

4.2.5 Galley language visibility for editors

In the editorial interface, each galley's language is now explicitly displayed in the galley grid. This improves transparency in multilingual publishing workflows and helps editors manage multiple language versions of the same article more reliably.

4.2.6 Language-aware URL structure for discoverability

Language selection is now reflected in the URL path (e.g. `/en/`, `/fi/`), replacing the previous cookie-based implementation. Each language version of a page receives its own unique and crawlable URL, enabling search engines and other automated services to index all available language versions. This change ensures that multilingual metadata and journal pages are fully discoverable and that multilingual versions are not hidden from crawlers.

Feature / Area	Before (pre-3.5)	After (OJS 3.5)
Coupling of UI, submission, and metadata languages	All language settings were tied to installed UI locales. Metadata and submission languages could not be configured independently.	UI, submission, and metadata languages are fully decoupled. Journals can independently choose which languages are available for UI, submission, and metadata.

Support for metadata languages (BCP 47)	Limited to languages with OJS-provided application locales. Many regional, minority, or script-specific languages were excluded.	Metadata languages follow BCP 47, providing 700+ valid codes including script and regional variants (e.g., fr_CA, cnr_Cyrl). Metadata can use languages not available as UI locales.
Editing metadata for legacy content	Editing metadata required keeping old/unused locales active. Disabling a locale made metadata fields inaccessible.	Metadata editing is independent from submission languages. Legacy metadata can be edited even if that language is disabled for new submissions.
Submission primary language management	Submission language was fixed and not clearly visible or editable in later workflow stages. Mismatches between content language and stored metadata were common.	Submission language is clearly visible and editable at any stage in the workflow. Changing it triggers required metadata fields for the new language.
Galley language visibility	Galley languages were not clearly shown in editorial grids, making multilingual version management error-prone.	Each galley's language is explicitly displayed in the galley grid, improving clarity for multilingual workflows.
URL structure for multilingual pages	Language selection relied on cookies. No separate language-specific URLs existed. Search engines could not index multiple language versions.	URLs now include the language code (e.g., /en/, /fi/). Each language version has a unique, crawlable URL, improving discoverability and Search Engine Optimization (SEO).

Table 3: T4.1 Multilingualism work: overview of developed features.

4.3 Github issues and pull requests for multilingualism features

The following list documents the core GitHub issues and pull requests related to the multilingualism work carried out in the CRAFT-OA Task 4.1. Each entry links to the technical implementation of specific multilingual features in OJS 3.5 and related PKP applications (OMP, OPS, and shared libraries).

Task	T4.1 Multilingualism
Subtask	Remove separate Dublin Core Language metadata field and only use Submission Locale to define the language
Github issue	https://github.com/pkp/pkp-lib/issues/5000
Pull request and comments	PKP: #9380 OJS: pkp/ojs#4057 OMP: pkp/omp#1469 OPS: pkp/ops#577 QuickSubmit: pkp/quickSubmit#76 CitationStyleLanguage: pkp/citationStyleLanguage#117

Table 4: T4.1 Multilingualism work in Github: Remove separate Dublin Core Language metadata field and only use Submission Locale to define the language.

Task	T4.1 Multilingualism
Subtask	Ensuring That All Languages Are Indexable by Crawlers
Github issue	https://github.com/pkp/pkp-lib/issues/699
Pull request and comments	PKP: #9628 OJS: pkp/ojs#4146 OMP: pkp/omp#1545 OPS: pkp/ops#659 Crossref-ojs: pkp/crossref-ojs#47 Crossref-ops: pkp/crossref-ops#37 CitationStyleLanguage: pkp/citationStyleLanguage#119 GoogleScholar: pkp/googleScholar#19

Table 5: T4.1 Multilingualism work in Github: Ensuring That All Languages Are Indexable by Crawlers.

Task	T4.1 Multilingualism
Subtask	Article language editable and clearly visible in the UI
Github issue	https://github.com/pkp/pkp-lib/issues/5502
Pull request and comments	PKP: #9245 UI: pkp/ui-library#280 OJS: pkp/ojs#4016 OMP: pkp/omp#1451 OPS: pkp/ops#563

Table 6: T4.1 Multilingualism work in Github: Article language editable and clearly visible in the UI.

Task	T4.1 Multilingualism
Subtask	Make article language selection and metadata forms independent from website language settings
Github issue	https://github.com/pkp/pkp-lib/issues/9425
Pull request and comments	PKP: #9309 OJS: pkp/ojs#4040 OMP: pkp/omp#1461 OPS: pkp/ops#569

Table 7: T4.1 Multilingualism work in Github: Make article language selection and metadata forms independent from website language settings.

Task	T4.1 Multilingualism
Subtask	Display galley language in the galley grid for editors
Github issue	https://github.com/pkp/pkp-lib/issues/9976
Pull request and comments	OPS: pkp/ops#687 OJS: pkp/ojs#4283

Table 8: T4.1 Multilingualism work in Github: Display galley language in the galley grid for editors.

5 METADATA QUALITY AND EXTENSIBILITY

The metadata quality and extensibility work described in this section is part of CRAFT-OA Work Package 4: Journal Software and Platform Improvement, under Task 4.3. The development work has been done by the Federation of Finnish Learned Societies (TSV) and the TIB – Leibniz Information Centre for Science and Technology and University Library. It focuses on strengthening the structure and interoperability of metadata in OJS through the introduction of controlled vocabularies, machine-readable contributor metadata, support for Contributor Role Taxonomy (CRedit) contributor roles, data citation capabilities, and automated metadata checks. Together, these improvements establish a foundation for more accurate, connected, and standards-compliant metadata across PKP applications.

5.1 Challenges in metadata quality and extensibility

OJS provides a well-structured metadata model that supports comprehensive description of journal articles. Within the CRAFT-OA project, the goal was to further strengthen this foundation by adding support for standardized, controlled vocabularies and improving the machine readability of metadata. These developments aim to enhance interoperability with external systems such as Crossref, DataCite, Open Researcher and Contributor ID (ORCID), and OpenAIRE Graph, and to ensure that OJS metadata aligns with current standards for structured and linked scholarly information.

5.1.1 Contributor metadata

Contributor information in OJS is managed through the *Users & Roles* system, where roles are primarily designed for permission management rather than metadata classification. Each user group (e.g., Author, Translator, Reviewer) is attached to a general permission level such as `ROLE_ID_AUTHOR` or `ROLE_ID_REVIEWER`. Because these role names can be freely modified by each journal, the system has no consistent way to identify contributor types programmatically.

As a result, application code and plugins use inconsistent and unreliable methods to determine contributor roles. For example:

- The Citation Style Language plugin requires manual configuration of which roles are treated as Authors or Translators.
- The ORCID plugin interprets English role labels, which breaks if the names are localized or renamed.
- The Crossref export treats all contributors as Authors, ignoring distinctions between authors, translators, and other contributor roles.

This model produces ambiguous and inconsistent metadata exports, prevents reliable automation, and makes it impossible to align contributor data with external systems that require explicit role classification.

All contributors are also stored in a database table named *authors*, which supports only persons. There is no native way to record organizations or collectives as contributors. Journals often work around this by entering organization names (e.g., “Editorial Board”) as personal names, which leads to poor metadata quality and limits interoperability with external registries and persistent identifier systems.

OJS supports the [CRedit](#) through a dedicated plugin. The plugin lets editors assign standardized contributor roles – such as *Conceptualization*, *Data Curation*, and *Writing – Review & Editing* – to contributors during submission or metadata editing. The CRedit functionality is currently available only via the plugin and not integrated into the core OJS data model, which limits automation and interoperability across plugins and export formats.

5.1.2 Controlled vocabularies

OJS currently supports locally defined keyword lists but lacks structured handling for controlled vocabularies. Journals can create their own keyword lists or taxonomies, but these are stored only as literal text values with no ability to include identifiers (Uniform Resource Identifiers (URIs)) or source information. Consequently:

- The same term may appear multiple times with different meanings.
- There is no way to reference authoritative vocabularies such as Finnish YSO or Frascati Manual
- Schema recommendations which require vocabulary URIs or source attributes, cannot be followed.

While it is technically possible to develop plugins that fetch term suggestions from external sources, the underlying data model does not support linking metadata fields to external vocabularies or storing structured identifiers. This results in inconsistent implementations across plugins and applications and limits OJS’s ability to produce high-quality, interoperable metadata. Also, the integration of external vocabularies should be made easier. Plugins should have access to clear hooks or endpoints rather than needing to rely on workarounds such as injecting content with Smarty filters.

5.1.3 Data citations

In OJS 3.4 and earlier versions, there is no native support for data citations or for recording structured relationships between publications and datasets. While Crossref and DataCite both support dataset linking through metadata relationships such as *isSupplementedBy*, *isBasedOn*, and *references*, OJS cannot capture or export this information.

Currently, journals must include dataset references in free-text fields such as *Data Availability Statements* or *References*. This prevents accurate metadata exchange and makes it impossible for indexing services and repositories to recognize and link related data objects.

Structured data citation requires the ability to record:

- the dataset identifier (e.g., Digital Object Identifier (DOI)),
- the identifier type,
- the relationship type, and
- a short dataset description.

Without these elements, data cannot be linked to publications in a standardized or machine-readable way, resulting in incomplete metadata and reduced discoverability in research data infrastructures.

5.2 New metadata quality and extensibility features in OJS 3.5 and 3.6

With the release of OJS 3.5 and the upcoming OJS 3.6, several improvements have been introduced to enhance metadata quality, structure, and interoperability. These updates strengthen how OJS manages metadata for articles, contributors, and vocabularies, improving consistency across workflows and integration with external systems such as Crossref, DataCite, and ORCID.

5.2.1 Controlled vocabularies for metadata fields (OJS 3.5)

OJS 3.5 introduces structured support for controlled vocabularies in article metadata. Previously, journals could only use free-text entries for fields such as keywords or disciplines. The new functionality allows metadata terms to include persistent identifiers and vocabulary sources, enabling precise linking to standardized vocabularies.

The system supports integration with external services through plugins, allowing journals to connect to authoritative vocabularies such as national thesauri or domain-specific indexes. A reference implementation demonstrates integration with the Finnish *Finto* service.⁴

Originally scheduled for OJS 3.6, this feature was completed early and included in OJS 3.5, providing a foundation for structured, machine-readable metadata that improves discoverability and interoperability.

⁴ See <https://github.com/tsv-fi/externalVocab>.

Figure 4: Metadata fields like Keywords now include hooks that make it easy to use an external vocabulary with the field. These are attached using a simple custom plugin and the OJS core is now capable of saving also the identifier and the source of the keyword provided by the external vocabulary plugin.

5.2.2 Machine-readable contributor metadata (OJS 3.6)

OJS 3.6 introduces a new core contributor metadata model, separating contributor information from the user permission system. In earlier versions, contributor data was derived from *User Roles* such as *Author*, *Translator*, or *Reviewer*, which were primarily intended for permission management.

The new model defines a dedicated contributor taxonomy, making contributor information machine-readable and interoperable with external systems. It also allows the recording of the degree of contribution, offering a more granular and standardized representation of contributor roles in publication metadata. The role identifiers are based on Crossref schema.⁵

Contributor Roles		Add Role
ROLE NAME	ROLE IDENTIFIER	
Author	AUTHOR	...
Translator	TRANSLATOR	...
Illustrator	OTHER	...

Figure 5: OJS 3.6 will have an internal contributor role taxonomy independent from the user role settings in the system. Journals can add their own roles based on role identifiers like *AUTHOR* and *TRANSLATOR* assuring that all the contributor roles are machine readable and can be used in the code.

⁵ Crossref documentation for Contributor metadata:

<https://www.crossref.org/documentation/schema-library/markup-guide-metadata-segments/contributors/>.

Contributor types (OJS 3.6)

The contributor model has been expanded to include multiple contributor types, allowing journals to identify contributors as persons, organizations, or anonymous entities. This update enables accurate representation of collective and institutional authorship and improves compatibility with the metadata schemas used by Crossref and DataCite.⁶

The inclusion of organization contributors also supports linking to Research Organization Registry (ROR) Identifiers (IDs)⁷, enhancing interoperability with global research information systems.

Figure 6: Different contributor types will be supported in OJS 3.6. When adding a new contributor, the user will first select the type and the required contributor metadata will depend on this setting.

5.2.3 CRediT contributor roles (OJS 3.6)

OJS 3.6 adds support for the CRediT as part of the new contributor metadata framework. The implementation introduces a standardized list of contributor roles that can be assigned to individuals or organizations, independent of their user permissions within the system.

Editors can record one or more CRediT roles – such as *Conceptualization*, *Data Curation*, or *Writing – Review & Editing* – and specify the degree of contribution where relevant. This functionality ensures consistent, structured attribution and aligns OJS metadata with international scholarly communication standards.

⁶ Crossref documentation for Contributor metadata:

<https://www.crossref.org/documentation/schema-library/markup-guide-metadata-segments/contributors/>

⁷ Research Organization Registry (ROR) is a persistent identifier for organisations used mainly for affiliation and funder data. <https://ror.org/>.

CRedit roles and the degrees of contribution
Select the CRedit roles of the contributor and the degrees of contribution.

ROLE	DEGREE	
Select a new role (required) *	Degree	
Writing – Original Draft Preparator	Lead	Remove Role
Select a new role (required) *	Degree	
Formal Analysis		Remove Role
Add Another Role		

Figure 7: Contributor metadata form in the forthcoming OJS 3.6 includes functionality for adding CRedit Roles.

5.2.4 Data citations (OJS 3.6)

In OJS 3.4 and earlier versions, there is no native support for recording structured relationships between publications and datasets. To close this gap, we have implemented a new feature available in the upcoming OJS 3.6 release that enables journals to add and export standardized data citations in a machine-readable format.

The new functionality introduces dedicated metadata fields for:

- the dataset identifier (e.g., DOI),
- the identifier type,
- the relationship type
- creators of the dataset
- a short dataset description

These elements can be entered directly through the OJS metadata interface and will be included in Crossref and DataCite Extensible Markup Language (XML) exports following their respective schema requirements. This makes it possible to accurately represent data–publication links, improving interoperability with repositories and indexing services.

Data Citations [Add a new Data Citation](#)

This table allows users to add formal data citations, ensuring datasets are properly credited and appear alongside other references in the publication.

TITLE	
10.12345/example.dataset.2025 Simulated Urban Climate Data for Helsinki, 2020–2030	...

Figure 8: Data Citations can be enabled in the article metadata form allowing users to add structured data citations to the article metadata.

5.2.5 Automatic metadata checks

OJS currently does not provide a mechanism to ensure that submissions comply with indexing requirements or adhere to specific editorial rules defined for each submission. The implementation of an automated validation process would allow the system to systematically verify mandatory elements, such as the inclusion of an abstract, and deliver immediate feedback to editors. Moreover, such a mechanism could prevent the publication of submissions that fail to meet the established standards.

The *Publication Validator* plugin interacts with OJS-Core for versions 3.3, 3.4 and 3.5, and validates mandatory article metadata for indexing in external services such as Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ). It provides the flexibility to add services in the future for services e.g. Web of Science. It checks essential fields including title, DOI, publisher, language, abstract, author list, author affiliation, and International Standard Serial Number (ISSN), helping ensure articles meet indexing requirements.

Figure 9: Validator prohibits publication due to missing fields required for DOAJ indexing service.

Feature / Area	Before (pre-3.5 / pre-3.6)	After (OJS 3.5 / 3.6)
Controlled vocabularies for metadata fields (OJS 3.5)	Metadata fields such as keywords and disciplines allowed only free-text entries. No support for identifiers, sources, or external vocabularies.	Structured vocabularies supported. Terms may include persistent identifiers and sources. Plugins can connect to external vocabularies (e.g., national thesauri). Provides machine-readable, standardized metadata.

Machine-readable contributor metadata (OJS 3.6)	Contributor data tied to user roles (Author, Translator, Reviewer), which were intended for permissions, not metadata. Not machine-readable for external systems.	New contributor metadata model with a separate contributor taxonomy. Contributor roles become machine-readable and interoperable with other systems.
Contributor types (OJS 3.6)	Contributors assumed to be individuals. No structured support for organizational or anonymous contributors. Limited compatibility with metadata schemas requiring organizational authors.	Supports multiple contributor types: persons, organizations, anonymous contributors. Improves representation of group or institutional authorship.
CRedit contributor roles (OJS 3.6)	No built-in support for contributor role taxonomies.	Adds full support for CRedit taxonomy. Editors can assign standardized contributor roles (e.g., Conceptualization, Data Curation). Supports multiple roles per contributor and optional degree of contribution.
Data citations (OJS 3.6)	No built-in structured metadata for linking articles to datasets. Data to publication relationships could not be stored or exported in standardized formats.	Introduces native data citation fields: dataset identifier (e.g. DOI), identifier type, relationship type, dataset creators, description. Fully included in Crossref and DataCite XML exports. Enables machine-readable data to publication links.

Automatic metadata checks (3.3–3.5 via plugin)	No mechanism to validate metadata against indexing requirements or editorial rules. Editors had to manually verify completeness (titles, abstracts, authors, affiliations, etc.).	Publication Validator plugin checks mandatory metadata fields for indexing (e.g., DOAJ). Validates elements such as title, DOI, publisher, language, abstract, author list, affiliations, ISSN. Prevents publication of incomplete metadata and supports future extensions (e.g., Web of Science).
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Table 9: T4.3 Metadata quality and extensibility work in Github: overview of developed features.

5.3 Github issues and pull requests for metadata features

The following list documents the core GitHub issues and pull requests related to the metadata quality and extensibility work carried out in CRAFT-OA Task 4.3. Each entry links to the technical implementation of the new metadata features developed for OJS 3.5 and 3.6, as well as related updates across PKP applications (OMP, OPS, and shared libraries).

Task	T4.3 Metadata quality and extensibility
Subtask	Supporting Controlled Vocabularies
Github issue	https://github.com/pkp/pkp-lib/issues/1550
Pull request / branches	https://github.com/pkp/ojs/pull/4617 https://github.com/pkp/pkp-lib/pull/10833 https://github.com/pkp/ui-library/pull/493 https://github.com/pkp/ops/pull/859 https://github.com/pkp/omp/pull/1829
Example plugin using the new features	https://github.com/tsv-fi/externalVocab

Table 10: T4.3 Metadata quality and extensibility work in Github: Supporting Controlled Vocabularies.

Task	T4.3 Metadata quality and extensibility
Subtask	Add support for CRediT standard for contributor attribution
Github issue	https://github.com/pkp/pkp-lib/issues/857
Pull request / branches	https://github.com/jyhein/ojs/tree/f857_credit https://github.com/jyhein/pkp-lib/tree/f857_credit https://github.com/jyhein/ui-library/tree/f857_credit

Table 11: T4.3 Metadata quality and extensibility work in Github: Add support for CRediT standard for contributor attribution.

Task	T4.3 Metadata quality and extensibility
Subtask	Machine-Readable Contributor Roles and support publications authored by organizations and anonymous authors
Github issue	https://github.com/pkp/pkp-lib/issues/11379
Pull request / branches	https://github.com/jyhein/ojs/tree/f857 https://github.com/jyhein/pkp-lib/tree/f857 https://github.com/jyhein/ui-library/tree/f857

Table 12: T4.3 Metadata quality and extensibility work in Github: Machine-Readable Contributor Roles and support publications authored by organizations and anonymous authors.

Task	T4.3 Metadata quality and extensibility
Subtask	Enable Data Citations
Github issue	https://github.com/pkp/pkp-lib/issues/6278
Pull request / branches	https://github.com/ajnyga/ui-library/tree/f6278 https://github.com/ajnyga/pkp-lib/tree/f6278

Table 13: T4.3 Metadata quality and extensibility work in Github: Enable Data Citations.

Task	T4.3 Metadata quality and extensibility
Subtask	Metadata Check Plugin (OJS 3.3, 3.5)
Branches	https://github.com/withanage/publicationValidator/tree/stable-3.3.0 https://github.com/withanage/publicationValidator/tree/stable-3.5.0
Pull requests	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> https://github.com/withanage/PublicationValidator/pull/1 https://github.com/withanage/PublicationValidator/pull/2 https://github.com/withanage/PublicationValidator/pull/3 https://github.com/withanage/PublicationValidator/pull/4 https://github.com/withanage/PublicationValidator/pull/5 https://github.com/withanage/PublicationValidator/pull/6

Table 14: T4.3 Metadata quality and extensibility work in Github: Metadata Check Plugin.

Task	T4.3 Metadata quality and extensibility
Subtask	Crossref Plugin validation extensions
Branches	https://github.com/pkp/crossref-ojs/branches/all
Pull requests	https://github.com/pkp/crossref-ojs/pull/71

Table 15: T4.3 Metadata quality and extensibility work in Github: Crossref Plugin validation extensions.

6 REFERENCES

6.1 List of References

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Phillips, A., & Davis, M. (2009). Tags for Identifying Languages (RFC 5646: Best Current Practice 47). Internet Engineering Task Force. Retrieved from <https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/html/rfc5646>.

6.2 List of Websites

Contributor Role Taxonomy (CRediT) – <https://credit.niso.org/>

Crossref Documentation – <https://www.crossref.org/documentation/>.

Github – <https://github.com/>.

PKP Community Forum – <https://forum.pkp.sfu.ca/>.

Public Knowledge Project – <https://pkp.sfu.ca/>.

Research Organization Registry (ROR) – <https://ror.org/>.

TIB – Leibniz Information Centre for Science and Technology and University Library – <https://www.tib.eu/en>.

The Federation of Finnish Learned Societies – <https://tsv.fi/en>.

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